

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY AT SCHOOL TO PRIMARY CLASSES

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Annotation. This given article aims to reveal what is teaching vocabulary in the foreign language. It's role, importance and necessity in English language. Also it shows the ways and stages how to develop it in. It also discusses lexical and analytical importance in the English language. The author of this article shares his knowledge about how the term of vocabulary appeared in linguistics, comparison of learning process among learners in English and their native language. In addition, there are described the most common mistakes in students speech and their usage in the given language.

Key words: words, phrases, vocabulary, learning-process, difficulty, games pronunciation problems.

INTRODUCTION.

In a recent years demand for learning is increasing step by step. The main reason for this is period changing from time to time and increasing foreign technologies and gadgets. In order to be aware of them, individuals should know and they should have ability, they should learn one specific foreign language and speaking in this. As English is widely used all over the world, there is a need for learners to acquire the communication skills of it to get success in their respective fields. Thus, the classroom is the ideal platform to acquire good communication skills, especially, speaking skills. The teachers have to understand the problems of the ELLS (English language learners) and try to implement various teaching strategies in their classrooms in order to develop their learners' speaking skills in English classrooms. Then the kinds of speaking situations and the main advantages of speaking skills are explained elaborately. Furthermore, this paper also supplies several techniques to develop speaking skills.

At this point it is important to mention that oral language development follows a sequence from single words to more and more complex phrases. Children learn to listen and to talk long before they learn to read and write. The same sequence should be followed in classroom teaching. Extra difficulty would be created if one would try to develop English reading and writing skills before children can speak the language. In order to be able to speak the language, students need to know some vocabulary first. In this paper I will focus on how to teach vocabulary that enables students to construct a rich vocabulary bank. Guiding methods are introduced and sample activities are provided.

RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGIES

VOCABULARY DEVELOPMENT IN THE PRIMARY GRADES.

A well-rounded reading curriculum should incorporate both direct and indirect teaching techniques to help pupils expand their oral and reading vocabulary. Read-alouds, group writing and reading projects, and independent reading are examples of indirect methods. Students' needs should be taken into account when teaching vocabulary directly, and

they should be actively involved in the process. All word learning tasks are not equal in difficulty. A child may understand the concept behind a word, but not know the word itself. For example, the word cease represents a known concept to most children; however, a young child has probably not heard this word used for stop. Learning a new word that represents a known concept is not as difficult as learning a new word that represents a new concept. Teachers in the primary grades introduce many new concepts, and direct instruction is necessary to build up the understanding of these concepts and the vocabulary words that represent them. The context of a word should always be stressed when teaching vocabulary words that stand in for well-known topics. Students' understanding of a term will be developed by providing a definition and discussing the word's significance within the reading selection. Students need to be exposed to this word often and in a range of settings if they are to learn it and include it in their vocabulary. Additionally, they must be given the chance to practice using the word in written or spoken communication.

MEMORY AND STORAGE SYSTEMS.

Understanding how our memory works might help us create more effective ways to teach vocabulary. Research in the area, cited by Gairns and Redman (1986) offers us some insights into this process. It seems that learning new items involve storing them first in our short-term memory, and afterwards in long-term memory. We do not control this process consciously but there seem to be some important clues to consider. First, retention in short-term memory is not effective if the number of chunks of information exceeds seven. Therefore, this suggests that in a given class we should not aim at teaching more than this number. However, our long-term memory can hold any amount of information.

However, as they depend on students' experiences and reality to support learning, meaningful tasks appear to provide the ideal solution for vocabulary acquisition. In addition to requiring learners to analyze and process language more thoroughly, more meaningful assignments should aid in the retention of information in long-term memory. It appears that forgetting is an inevitable process unless students make regular use of the knowledge they have acquired. Recycling is therefore essential and should ideally take place one or two days following the original input. Testing on previously taught material can then be done on a weekly or monthly basis. Students' success or failure in recovering knowledge when needed can also be attributed to how they store what they have learnt. The majority of students just jot down what they have learned in chronological order, including translations where necessary. The decontextualization of the items in this system encourages students to overgeneralize their usage, which makes it far from beneficial. It does not specify pronunciation and does not permit additions or modifications. Instructors can also urge students to organize a notebook, binder, or index card using subjects and categories. English should be used as often as possible to store meaning. Word clouds and diagrams can also be applied to this topic/category structure. A vocabulary box containing cards can be kept by the entire class and used frequently for review and recycling.

DISCUSSION

WAYS OF TEACHING VOCABULARY

The question is which strategies are most successful in teaching vocabulary? Vocabulary instruction which requires active student involvement seems to improve comprehension more than passive vocabulary activities. Other than free voluntary reading and the teaching of

words that are essential to the learning of specific concepts, there seems to be no strategy that is consistently superior. Methods using a variety of techniques seem to be advantageous. Repeated exposure to chosen words aids in learning those words. Good teaching provides the learner with strategies not only for learning the task at hand but for independent learning beyond the task at hand. Students should be responsible for learning a variety of methods to acquire word meanings. Active involvement and deep processing of words are important. Students should connect words to meaningful contexts or known synonyms.

We must first define concepts in order to proceed. Concepts are the bigger network of intellectual relationships that arise from categorization and the categories into which experiences are structured. Making links between words and concepts based on predetermined criteria demands a certain amount of critical thinking, which is necessary for comprehending a notion. Concept categories are used to group things or events based on essential or fundamental qualities. For a characteristic to be placed in a category, it must be present in a specific order, connection, or pattern. These stand in for the concept requirements. The notion of definition or rule refers to the particular arrangement of qualities. A student's vocabulary - the words he or she can understand when reading and listening and use when writing and speaking are critical to success in school. This is the reason why vocabulary is an essential element of effective language teaching. So how do students learn all the words they need to know? The combination of direct instruction and wide reading is a good formula for word learning. In the following overview I will briefly mention some methods that encourage word learning. The direct instruction is explicit teaching of carefully selected words which improves understanding and helps students' vocabulary grow. Often, it is best to pre-teach key words.

CONCLUSION.

Teachers may wonder why it is important to teach vocabulary. Well, there is a very clear answer to that question, namely that vocabulary is critical to reading success for three reasons, which I will explain now briefly. First of all, comprehension improves when you know what the words mean. Since comprehension is the ultimate goal of reading, you cannot overestimate the importance of vocabulary development. Secondly, words are the currency of communication. A robust vocabulary improves all areas of communication which are listening, speaking, reading and writing. Last but not least, when children and adolescents improve their vocabulary, their academic and social confidence and competence improve, too.

Many young learners may see main possible problems which we face to learn by harda new words in everyday if they do not analyze what is word and what is meaning of this word's defination. Young learners absolutely face to many challenges because simpe memorization is not enough as I said above. Students need a wide range of independent word-learning strategies. Vocabulary instruction should

aim to engage students in actively thinking about word meanings, the relationships among words, and how we can use words in different situations. This type of rich, deep instruction is most likely to influence comprehension. For many students, it is easier to remember a word's meaning by making a quick sketch that connects the word to something personally meaningful to the student. The student applies each target word to a new, familiar context. The student does not have to spend a lot of time making a great drawing. The important thing is that the sketch makes sense and helps the student connect with the meaning of the word. The

ability to analyze word parts also helps when students are faced with unknown vocabulary. If students know the meanings of root words and affixes, they are more likely to understand a word containing these word parts.

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